

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear J.UCS Readers,

This is the last issue of J.UCS Vol. 16 (2010) presenting, as usually, a mixture of topics as is typical for J.UCS. Hence it is time for some reflections on major events that have taken place: some good, some very sad. Let me start with the good news.

The impact factor of J.UCS has now reached 0.669 (compared to 0.488 a year ago), a very significant increase, and the growth of the 5-year impact factor over the last year from 0.428 to 0.788 is even more impressive. We thank authors and members of our editorial board for making this important increase possible!

A further growth of J.UCS is also noticeable in other numbers. The number of files downloaded has grown in the four years 2007- 2010 continuously from 5,5 million to 8,1 million. This corresponds to an unbelievable 263 Terabytes in 2010 compared to already impressive 145 Terabytes in 2007.

Some may have noticed that the composition of the team of editors-in-chief has changed. Klaus Tochtermann who has left the Institute for Knowledge Management in Graz, Austria, to become head of the Leibnitz Library in Kiel, Germany, has been replaced by Michael Granitzer, the Scientific Director of the Know Center, Austria. We thank the outgoing editor-in-chief for his valuable help over some 10 years, and we welcome our new team member. We are confident that he will be as active as his predecessor.

Unfortunately, this has also been a year reminding us very much of our vulnerabilities. We could still celebrate the 70th birthday of our friend and long term member of our editorial board Derick Wood with a special issue in his honour (http://www.jucs.org/jucs_16_5/). However, already frail when the issue appeared, Derick passed away on October 4, 2010. We have lost a good friend and grieve with his family.

May 2011 only bring pleasant surprises.

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

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